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Review Article

ROLE OF EMERGENCY TISSUE PLASMINOGEN ACTIVATOR IN ISCHEMIC STROKE

Tissue plasminogen activator efficiency in ischemic stroke.

Mohammed ahmed alhejaily¹, Majed Meshal Almutairi², Ahmad Abdulghani Alzaidi³, Fahad Abdullah Ali Alshehri⁴, Abdulrahman Bader AlAql⁵, Muhammad Abdullah M Almalki⁶, Mohammed Ahmed Almasabi⁷, Abdulmajeed Hamed Alhamyani⁸, Faisal Fawzi Abuhalimeh⁹

¹surgical resident, Ohud Hospital, Saudi Arabia, Alhejailymohammed@gmail.com, ²Medical College, Imam Mohammad Bin Saud University, Saudi Arabia Maj88999@hotmail.com, ³Medical College, Taif University, Saudi Arabia ahmadalzaidi92@gmail.com, ⁴Medical College, University of Science and Technology, Yemem, Dr.fahad.alshehri@gmail.com, ⁵Medical College, Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia, Dr.Abdulrahman.b.alaqi@gmail.com, ⁶Medical College, Northern Borders University, Saudi Arabia, Mbbs.141214@gmail.com, ⁷Medical College, King Khaled University, Saudi Arabia m-a-m-4@hotmail.com, ⁸Medical College, Taif University, Saudi Arabia Alhiila-511@hotmail.com, ⁹Al Imam Muhammad Ibn Saud Islamic University, College of Medicine, Faiabuhlimeh@hotmail.com

Abstract

Background:

Intravenous tissue plasminogen activator (t-PA) was recognized and approved as the thrombolytic agent for acute ischemic stroke that can improve patients' outcome and resolve their neurological deficits. The main reason for the difficulty of stroke treatment is the narrow time window. The cost-effectiveness and feasibility of intravenous t-PA for treatment of acute stroke in 3 - 4.5 hour time window, after symptom onset, have been confirmed in previous studies.

Aim: To determine the role of emergency tissue plasminogen activator in ischemic stroke. Also, to study its risk factors, complications, regulatory approvals and its efficiency with time.

Methods: The data were obtained after searching the available studies published in English language using several key words (tissue plasminogen activator, ischemic stroke, efficiency and role) on the scientific websites as Pubmed, ResearchGate, and Google scholar.

Results: This study included 27 randomized and non randomized trials as well as systemic reviews. The data were extracted according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the time of treatment, the dosage, follow up and the history of the patients. The included articles were published between the years 2000 to 2018.

Conclusion: The results of this study indicated that the administration of intravenous rt-PA among stroke patients could reduce the unfavorable outcome and increase the quality of life as well the neurological activity. After acute ischemic stroke, the guidelines suggest using rt-PA within 3 -4.5 h after the initiation of the stroke to achieve the best outcomes and decrease the risk of hemorrhage.

Keywords: Emergency, tissue plasminogen activator, ischemic stroke, safety, side effects.

Corresponding author:

Mohammed ahmed alhejaily,
surgical resident, Ohud Hospital, Saudi Arabia,
Alhejailymohammed@gmail.com.

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INTRODUCTION:

Stroke is a chief basis of mortality in the United States and about 800,000 new strokes are reported each year (1, 2). It is associated with high rates of disability among elder stroke patients (1).

During the treatment of acute ischemic stroke, the administration of intravenous tissue-type plasminogen activator (IV tPA) is the only approved treatment for lysis of the thrombus (3). Since the approval of t-PA in 1996, the number of ischemic stroke patients treated with t-PA has been increased but still low than the proper number as only rate 3.4% to 5.2% of all American AIS patients were treated with t-PA (4). The rate of using rt-PA is associated with the delay of emergency medical services, the process and time of treatment initiation, and the time window for each treatment (5). Current efforts are done to rise the treatment rate for IV tPA to all patients with stroke who are eligible and present within 2 hours from the onset of the symptoms (6). Some studies proved that the usage and enlargement of telestroke networks are related to enhancing the usage of IV tPA treatment (7, 8).

Also, in order to increase the treatment rates, the therapeutic time window must be expanded as the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved the usage of IV tPA treatment patients suffering from AIS within 3 hours of the onset of stroke symptoms. On the other hand, some other studies showed that efficacy and safety of using rt-PA with extending the time window more than 3 hours then treatment time window was expanded to <4.5 hours in Europe and other countries (9-11).

One of the most common complications resulting in high mortality and morbidity rates is intracerebral hemorrhage thus adherence to the clinical guidelines during rt-PA treatment among stroke patients could be associated with decreasing the risk of hemorrhage and increase the efficiency of other stroke medications (12, 13). In this review, we aimed at determining the role of emergency tissue plasminogen activator in ischemic stroke. Also, to study its risk factors, complications, regulatory approvals and its efficiency with time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The data were obtained after searching the available studies published in English language using several key words (tissue plasminogen activator, ischemic stroke, efficiency and role) on the scientific websites as Pubmed, ResearchGate, Google scholar,etc. After the first search, 30 studies were available then 3 studies were excluded. This study included 27 randomized and non randomized trials as well as

systemic reviews. The data were extracted according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the time of treatment, the dosage, follow up and the history of the patients. The included articles were published between the years 2000 to 2018.

Discussion:

Tissue Plasminogen Activator in Stroke: Dosage and Time Window

Intravenous t-PA was documented as the appropriate thrombolytic factor that can improve the neurological deficits and outcomes among acute ischemic stroke patients. Stroke treatment is mainly difficult due to the narrow time window resulting in decreasing the suitability of using t-PA among stroke patients (14). Large studies were conducted to study the efficiency and safety margins of t-PA among patients suffering from acute ischemic stroke. These studies suggested that the proper dosage of t-PA is 0.9 mg/kg up during the first 4 hours of the onset of stroke (3, 10, 15-21).

Interestingly, the earlier treatment is favorable resulting in decreasing the complications of stroke patients within 3 h of the onset of stroke and its efficiency is decreased with time, age and the timing of initiation of treatment and those treated between 3-6 h showed higher incidence of death rates among the patients (22-27).

The profits of t-PA among stroke patients

The treatment of stroke patients using t-PA within the time window (3-4.5 h) would give favorable outcomes among most of included patients and increase the quality of life (18, 20, 21, 28-31). A study showed that the quality of life was adjusted and the health benefits were increased when compared to those who didn't receive t-PA treatment within the time window (29). Also, other studies proved that the t-PA usage could be associated with better outcomes and less adverse effects but associated with age, sex, and duration of stroke (32, 33).

The complications of t-PA among stroke patients

Some clinical trials studied the adverse effects of the t-PA showed that the rates of death were slightly larger if treated with t-PA after 3 hours till 6 hours (9, 27, 34, 35). The most common reported and serious complication of rt-PA therapy during stroke is intracranial hemorrhage (ICH) (14, 34, 36). Also, a clinical trials showed that the incidence of ICH after rt-PA is affected by the ethnicity, differences in coagulation and fibrinolytic factors (37). However, other trials showed no significant difference in the incidence of symptomatic intracranial

haemorrhage among stroke patients treated with rt-PA within 3 h when compared to those who received them after 3-6 hours (22, 27, 34).

CONCLUSION:

The results of this study indicated that the administration of intravenous rt-PA among stroke patients could reduce the unfavorable outcome and increase the quality of life as well the neurological activity. After acute ischemic stroke, the guidelines suggest using rt-PA within 3 -4.5 h after the initiation of the stroke to achieve the best outcomes and decrease the risk of hemorrhage. Large population clinical trials must be conducted to investigate the adverse effects and the dosage as well as identifying the high risk intracranial hemorrhage patients after treating with rt-PA.

REFERENCES:

1. Go AS, Mozaffarian D, Roger VL, Benjamin EJ, Berry JD, Blaha MJ, et al. Heart disease and stroke statistics--2014 update: a report from the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. 2014;129(3):e28-e292.
2. Murphy SL, Xu J, Kochanek KD. Deaths: final data for 2010. *Natl Vital Stat Rep*. 2013;61(4):1-117.
3. Cheng NT, Kim AS. Intravenous Thrombolysis for Acute Ischemic Stroke Within 3 Hours Versus Between 3 and 4.5 Hours of Symptom Onset. *The Neurohospitalist*. 2015;5(3):101-9.
4. Adeoye O, Hornung R, Khatri P, Kleindorfer D. Recombinant tissue-type plasminogen activator use for ischemic stroke in the United States: a doubling of treatment rates over the course of 5 years. *Stroke*. 2011;42(7):1952-5.
5. (CASPR) IC. Prioritizing interventions to improve rates of thrombolysis for ischemic stroke. *Neurology*. 2005;64(4):654-9.
6. Katzan IL. Improvement in stroke performance measures: are we moving forward or in circles? *Circulation Cardiovascular quality and outcomes*. 2011;4(5):493-5.
7. Chalouhi N, Dressler JA, Kunkel ES, Dalyai R, Jabbour P, Gonzalez LF, et al. Intravenous tissue plasminogen activator administration in community hospitals facilitated by telestroke service. *Neurosurgery*. 2013;73(4):667-71; discussion 71-2.
8. Hess DC, Wang S, Hamilton W, Lee S, Pardue C, Waller JL, et al. REACH: clinical feasibility of a rural telestroke network. *Stroke*. 2005;36(9):2018-20.
9. Hacke W, Kaste M, Bluhmki E, Brozman M, Davalos A, Guidetti D, et al. Thrombolysis with alteplase 3 to 4.5 hours after acute ischemic stroke. *N Engl J Med*. 2008;359(13):1317-29.
10. Del Zoppo GJ, Saver JL, Jauch EC, Adams HP, Jr. Expansion of the time window for treatment of acute ischemic stroke with intravenous tissue plasminogen activator: a science advisory from the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association. *Stroke*. 2009;40(8):2945-8.
11. Fonarow GC, Smith EE, Saver JL, Reeves MJ, Bhatt DL, Grau-Sepulveda MV, et al. Timeliness of tissue-type plasminogen activator therapy in acute ischemic stroke: patient characteristics, hospital factors, and outcomes associated with door-to-needle times within 60 minutes. *Circulation*. 2011;123(7):750-8.
12. Saver JL. Hemorrhage after thrombolytic therapy for stroke: the clinically relevant number needed to harm. *Stroke*. 2007;38(8):2279-83.
13. Kase CS, Furlan AJ, Wechsler LR, Higashida RT, Rowley HA, Hart RG, et al. Cerebral hemorrhage after intra-arterial thrombolysis for ischemic stroke: the PROACT II trial. *Neurology*. 2001;57(9):1603-10.
14. Briosa EGD, Almeida A, Monteiro N. Successful Thrombolysis despite Having an Incidental Unruptured Cerebral Aneurysm. *Case reports in neurological medicine*. 2014;2014:323049.
15. Kasmaei HD, Baratloo A, Nasiri Z, Soleymani M, Yazdani MO. Recombinant tissue plasminogen activator administration in patients with cerebrovascular accident; a case series. *Archives of Neuroscience*. 2015;2(2).
16. DeMers G, Meurer WJ, Shih R, Rosenbaum S, Vilke GM. Tissue plasminogen activator and stroke: review of the literature for the clinician. *The Journal of emergency medicine*. 2012;43(6):1149-54.
17. Ahmed N, Wahlgren N, Grond M, Hennerici M, Lees KR, Mikulik R, et al. Implementation and outcome of thrombolysis with alteplase 3-4.5 h after an acute stroke: an updated analysis from SITS-ISTR. *Lancet Neurol*. 2010;9(9):866-74.
18. Xu ZP, Li HH, Li YH, Zhang Y, Wu Q, Lin L. Feasibility and outcomes of intravenous thrombolysis 3-4.5 hours after stroke in Chinese patients. *Journal of clinical neuroscience : official journal of the Neurosurgical Society of Australasia*. 2014;21(5):822-6.
19. Asaithambi G, Tong X, George MG, Tsai AW, Peacock JM, Luepker RV, et al. Acute stroke refusion therapy trends in the expanded treatment window era. *Journal of stroke and cerebrovascular diseases : the official journal of National Stroke Association*. 2014;23(9):2316-21.
20. Tekle WG, Chaudhry SA, Hassan AE, Peacock JM, Lakshminarayan K, Tsai A, et al. Utilization

- of intravenous thrombolysis in 3-4.5 hours: analysis of the Minnesota stroke registry. *Cerebrovascular diseases* (Basel, Switzerland). 2012;34(5-6):400-5.
21. Shobha N, Buchan AM, Hill MD. Thrombolysis at 3-4.5 hours after acute ischemic stroke onset--evidence from the Canadian Alteplase for Stroke Effectiveness Study (CASES) registry. *Cerebrovascular diseases* (Basel, Switzerland). 2011;31(3):223-8.
 22. Albers GW, Clark WM, Madden KP, Hamilton SA. ATLANTIS trial: results for patients treated within 3 hours of stroke onset. *Alteplase Thrombolysis for Acute Noninterventional Therapy in Ischemic Stroke*. *Stroke*. 2002;33(2):493-5.
 23. Ahmed N, Kellert L, Lees KR, Mikulik R, Tatlisumak T, Toni D. Results of intravenous thrombolysis within 4.5 to 6 hours and updated results within 3 to 4.5 hours of onset of acute ischemic stroke recorded in the Safe Implementation of Treatment in Stroke International Stroke Thrombolysis Register (SITS-ISTR): an observational study. *JAMA neurology*. 2013;70(7):837-44.
 24. Toni D, Ahmed N, Anzini A, Lorenzano S, Brozman M, Kaste M, et al. Intravenous thrombolysis in young stroke patients: results from the SITS-ISTR. *Neurology*. 2012;78(12):880-7.
 25. Lees KR, Bluhmki E, von Kummer R, Brott TG, Toni D, Grotta JC, et al. Time to treatment with intravenous alteplase and outcome in stroke: an updated pooled analysis of ECASS, ATLANTIS, NINDS, and EPITHET trials. *Lancet*. 2010;375(9727):1695-703.
 26. Emberson J, Lees KR, Lyden P, Blackwell L, Albers G, Bluhmki E, et al. Effect of treatment delay, age, and stroke severity on the effects of intravenous thrombolysis with alteplase for acute ischaemic stroke: a meta-analysis of individual patient data from randomised trials. *Lancet*. 2014;384(9958):1929-35.
 27. Sandercock P, Wardlaw JM, Lindley RI, Dennis M, Cohen G, Murray G, et al. The benefits and harms of intravenous thrombolysis with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator within 6 h of acute ischaemic stroke (the third international stroke trial [IST-3]): a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2012;379(9834):2352-63.
 28. Amiri A, Goudarzi R, Amiresmaili M, Iranmanesh F. Cost-effectiveness analysis of tissue plasminogen activator in acute ischemic stroke in Iran. *Journal of medical economics*. 2018;21(3):282-7.
 29. Tung CE, Win SS, Lansberg MG. Cost-effectiveness of tissue-type plasminogen activator in the 3- to 4.5-hour time window for acute ischemic stroke. *Stroke*. 2011;42(8):2257-62.
 30. Ehlers L, Andersen G, Clausen LB, Bech M, Kjolby M. Cost-effectiveness of intravenous thrombolysis with alteplase within a 3-hour window after acute ischemic stroke. *Stroke*. 2007;38(1):85-9.
 31. Goyal N, Male S, Al Wafai A, Bellamkonda S, Zand R. Cost burden of stroke mimics and transient ischemic attack after intravenous tissue plasminogen activator treatment. *Journal of stroke and cerebrovascular diseases : the official journal of National Stroke Association*. 2015;24(4):828-33.
 32. Mar J, Arrospide A, Comas M. Budget impact analysis of thrombolysis for stroke in Spain: a discrete event simulation model. *Value in health : the journal of the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research*. 2010;13(1):69-76.
 33. Fattahi a, azad a, Montazeri a. Quality of life among stroke patients in Kermanshah city. *Journal of Modern Rehabilitation*. 2008;2(1):1-8.
 34. Clark WM, Albers GW, Madden KP, Hamilton S. The rtPA (alteplase) 0- to 6-hour acute stroke trial, part A (A0276g) : results of a double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter study. *Thrombolytic therapy in acute ischemic stroke study investigators*. *Stroke*. 2000;31(4):811-6.
 35. Davis SM, Donnan GA, Parsons MW, Levi C, Butcher KS, Peeters A, et al. Effects of alteplase beyond 3 h after stroke in the Echoplanar Imaging Thrombolytic Evaluation Trial (EPITHET): a placebo-controlled randomised trial. *Lancet Neurol*. 2008;7(4):299-309.
 36. Aiyagari V, Gujjar A, Zazulia AR, Diringner MN. Hourly blood pressure monitoring after intravenous tissue plasminogen activator for ischemic stroke: does everyone need it? *Stroke*. 2004;35(10):2326-30.
 37. Ghandehari K. Barriers of thrombolysis therapy in developing countries. *Stroke research and treatment*. 2011;2011:686797.